

Supplementary Material

for

Dispatch optimization and sizing of molten-salt power-to-heat systems in balancing electricity markets for industrial heat electrification

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Introduction

This document provides detailed model formulations, detailed input data and additional results supporting the main manuscript. Nomenclature and References are provided at the end of this document.

1 Thermal Loss Model (S1)

Thermal losses $P_{\text{loss}}(t)$ are used in the dispatch optimization model in an energy balance equation which updates the State of Charge ($SoC(t)$) of the thermal energy storage (TES) system. Heat losses are evaluated at each time step and depend on the TES SoC, as higher stored energy (corresponding to a higher hot molten salt level) results in increased heat dissipation.

A one-dimensional steady-state heat transfer analysis is used to estimate heat losses from the TES system, i.e. storage tanks.

1.1 Model assumptions

A vertical-cylindrical tank with one layer of insulation is considered, as depicted in Fig. 1. The model also considers two height reserves: h_{MS} represents the portion of tank that must always be filled with molten salt to ensure MS pump operation and h_{air} is the buffer height between the maximum salt level and the tank roof. It is assumed that the tank is mounted on a supporting frame, i.e. it is surrounded by ambient air on all sides. The tank's inner volume is divided into two sections: a wet region (where MS is in contact with the wall) and a dry region (empty top part, where gas is in contact with the wall). The height of these sections (level of MS) changes with varying SoC of the TES system. Specific heat transfer coefficients are calculated for each section. This represents a widely used approach to account for the varying molten salt level in a storage tank, as demonstrated in several studies, including [1], [2], and [3]. The following simplifications were considered in the heat transfer analysis:

- i. the tank is modeled as a cylinder (disregarding the spherical shape of the bottom and roof), i.e. cylindrical conduction model is chosen for tank wall and planar conduction model for the roof and bottom
- ii. heat transfer by radiation is neglected
- iii. both fluids inside the tank have a uniform temperature distribution and same temperature, thus internal heat transfer between the fluids is neglected

Figure 1: TES tank's heat loss schematics

1.2 Model equations

Equations used to estimate hot tank heat losses are presented below. The formulation applies analogously to the cold tank. The total hot tank heat losses $P_{loss, HOT}$ are given by the sum of heat losses through the wet wall (Q_{wet}), the dry wall (Q_{dry}), tank's bottom (Q_b) and tank's roof (Q_r), as stated in Eq. (1). This can be expressed using Eq. (2), where the respective thermal resistances are considered.

$$P_{loss, HOT}(SoC) = Q_{wet, HOT}(SoC) + Q_{dry, HOT}(SoC) + Q_{b, HOT} + Q_{r, HOT} \quad (1)$$

$$P_{loss, HOT}(SoC) = \left(\frac{1}{R_{wet, HOT}(SoC)} + \frac{1}{R_{dry, HOT}(SoC)} + \frac{1}{R_{b, HOT}} + \frac{1}{R_{r, HOT}} \right) (T_{HOT} - T_{amb}) \quad (2)$$

The individual thermal resistances consider natural convective heat transfer inside and outside the tank as well as heat conduction through the vessel's wall and insulation. Eq. (3) is formulated for the wet wall but is equally applicable to the dry wall. Likewise, Eq. (4) describes the thermal resistance at the tank bottom and can also be used for the roof.

$$R_{\text{wet,hot}}(\text{SoC}) = \frac{1}{h_{\text{wet,hot}} A_{\text{wet,i,hot}}(\text{SoC})} + \frac{\ln\left(\frac{r_i+d_{\text{wall}}}{r_i}\right)}{2\pi L_{\text{wet}}(\text{SoC}) k_{\text{wall}}} + \frac{\ln\left(\frac{r_i+d_{\text{wall}}+d_{\text{ins}}}{r_i+d_{\text{wall}}}\right)}{2\pi L_{\text{wet}}(\text{SoC}) k_{\text{ins}}} + \frac{1}{h_{\text{amb}} A_{\text{wet,o,hot}}(\text{SoC})} \quad (3)$$

$$R_{\text{b,hot}} = \frac{1}{h_{\text{b,hot}} A_{\text{b, hot}}} + \frac{d_{\text{wall}}}{A_{\text{b,hot}} k_{\text{wall}}} + \frac{d_{\text{ins}}}{A_{\text{b,hot}} k_{\text{ins}}} + \frac{1}{h_{\text{amb}} A_{\text{b,hot}}} \quad (4)$$

In the equations above, h and k denote the heat transfer coefficient and thermal conductivity. Subscripts ‘wall’, ‘ins’, ‘i’, ‘o’, and ‘amb’ refer to wall, insulation, inner, outer, and ambient conditions.

The convective heat transfer between fluid inside the tank and its inner wall is approximated by a correlation for vertical cylinder using Eq.(5), while the heat transfer at the tank’s bottom and roof is estimated using a correlation for a horizontal plate using Eq. (6) [4].

$$Nu = 0.13 (Gr Pr)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (5)$$

$$Nu = 0.27 (Gr Pr)^{\frac{1}{4}} \quad (6)$$

Total heat losses, considering SoC-dependent losses from both cold and hot tank, are calculated using Eq. (7). The safety factor SF is also considered a conservative measure, to also account for losses in the piping system.

$$P_{\text{loss}}(\text{SoC}) = SF (P_{\text{loss, HOT}}(\text{SoC}) + P_{\text{loss, COLD}}(\text{SoC})) \quad (7)$$

1.3 Parametrization

To integrate heat losses into the MILP dispatch optimization model, they are approximated as a linear function of the TES SoC, as expressed in Eq.(8)

$$P_{\text{loss}}(t-1) = [c_0 + c_1 \cdot \text{SoC}(t-1)] \frac{E_{\text{TESnom}}}{E_{\text{TESref}}} \quad \forall t \in \tau \quad (8)$$

Total heat losses calculation is performed for the whole TES SoC operating range, which reflects varying MS level in the hot and cold tanks. Through linear approximation of the calculated data, the coefficients c_0 and c_1 of the linear function described in Eq. (8) are obtained. Furthermore, a modular system design is assumed, where increased storage capacity is achieved by adding identical units in parallel. As a result, total thermal losses scale proportionally with system size. To capture this effect, the loss term is scaled by the ratio of storage capacities. Here, E_{TESnom} denotes the nominal TES capacity of the specific case sizing, whereas E_{TESref} represents the TES capacity of the reference (base case) sizing scenario, which remains fixed at 10 MWh_{th}.

1.4 Input parameters

Input data for thermal loss estimation are summarized in Table 1. The thermophysical properties of YARA MOST can be found in [5]. Air properties were obtained from REFPROP.

Table 1: Input data for thermal loss calculation from TES tanks (base case sizing: 10 MWh_{th} TES capacity)

Parameter	Value	Unit
Tank diameter	3	m
Tank length	6.5	m
Minimum MS height	0.25	m
Minimum air height	0.25	m
Hot tank operational temperature	480	°C
Cold tank operational temperature	180	°C
Ambient temperature	20	°C
Wall thickness	8	mm
Insulation thickness	200	mm
Wall thermal conductivity	20	W/(m K)
Insulation conductivity	0.12	W/(m K)
Outside air heat transfer coefficient	5	W/(m ² K)
Safety factor SF	1.5	[-]

1.5 Results

The results of the thermal loss estimation for the base case sizing (TES capacity of 10 MWh_{th}) are shown in Fig. 2. The corresponding linear fit for total TES system thermal losses yields coefficients $c_0 = 33.59$ kW and $c_1 = 4.08$ kW.

The observed variation of heat losses with SoC is relatively weak; however, including this dependency in the MILP formulation enables the model to distinguish between different storage states during idle operation, e.g., between a fully charged hot tank and a cold tank.

Figure 2: Heat losses as a function of TES SoC for the base case. Markers represent results from the detailed heat transfer model, while dashed lines indicate the corresponding linear approximation.

2 Activated Capacity Ratio (S2)

The activation ratio, RE_{act} , represents the fraction of reserved capacity that is actually activated within a given hour. The activation ratio is one of the key parameters describing participation in the balancing market. Its value is based on engineering judgment and observed market behavior.

A decreasing trend of RE_{act} is assumed. This reflects a conservative modelling assumption that larger bid volumes are less likely to be fully activated in practice, due to system constraints and dispatch limitations.

2.1 Parametrization

The relationship between RE_{act} and the offered reserve capacity in the aFRR market is modelled using a linear function, as illustrated in Fig. 3. The fitted model is given by:

$$RE_{act} = c_0 + c_1 \cdot x \quad (9)$$

where x denotes the offered reserved capacity in MW.

The regression coefficients are: $c_0 = 0.85$ [-] and $c_1 = -0.01$ [MW^{-1}].

Figure 3: RE_{act} value for provided reserved capacity at aFRR market.

Nomenclature

A	Heat transfer area [m^2]
d	Wall/insulation thickness [m]
E_{TES}	Thermal energy storage capacity [MWh_{th}]
Gr	Grashof number [-]
h	Heat transfer coefficient [$W/(m^2K)$]
k	Thermal conductivity [$W/(mK)$]
L	Length [m]
Nu	Nusselt number [-]
P_{loss}	Thermal losses [kW]

Pr	Prandtl number [-]
Q	Heat transfer rate [W]
R	Thermal resistance [K/W]
r	Radius [m]
RE_{act}	Activation ratio [-]
SF	Safety factor [-]
SoC	State of Charge [-]
T	Temperature [K]
t	time [h]
aFRR	automatic Frequency Restoration Reserve
MILP	Mixed-Integer Linear Programming
MS	Molten Salt
REFPROP	Reference Fluid Thermodynamic and Transport Properties Database
SoC	State of Charge
TES	Thermal Energy Storage

References

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